

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL FOR THE PAPER “CHI-PLOTS FOR ASSESSING
MULTIVARIATE INDEPENDENCE” BY N.I. FISHER AND A.J. LEE

1. PROOF OF THEOREM 1

Let $U = (U_1, \dots, U_k)$ where $U_j = I(X_j \odot x_j)$ and X_j is the multivariate observation in block j . Let $P_j = E[U_j]$ and let $(U_{i1}, \dots, U_{ik}), i = 1, \dots, n$ be n independent realizations of U . Then

$$H_n = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \prod_{l=1}^k U_{il}$$

and

$$F_{ln} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n U_{il}.$$

Using the identity

$$\prod_{l=1}^k (a_l + b_l) = \sum_{c \in S_k} \prod_{l \in c} a_l \prod_{l \notin c} b_l$$

where S_k is the power set of $\{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} H_n &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \prod_{l=1}^k U_{il} \\ &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \prod_{l=1}^k (U_{il} - P_l + P_l) \\ &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{c \in S_k} \prod_{l \in c} (U_{il} - P_l) \prod_{l \notin c} P_l. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly,

$$F_{1n} \cdots F_{kn} = \sum_{c \in S_k} \prod_{l \in c} (\bar{U}_l - P_l) \prod_{l \notin c} P_l.$$

Now when the set c in these products is the empty set, or when c is a singleton, the corresponding terms in both H_n and $F_{1n} \cdots F_{kn}$ are the same so cancel out of the difference. For any other subset c in $\sqrt{n}F_{1n} \cdots F_{kn}$ we have a product containing a term of the form $\sqrt{n}(\bar{U}_l - P_l)$ (which converges in distribution to a normal), and one or more terms of the form $(\bar{U}_l - P_l)$ (which converge in probability to zero). It follows (since $O_P(1)o_p(1) = o_p(1)$) that

$$\sqrt{n} \sum_{c \in S_k^*} \prod_{l \in c} (\bar{U}_l - P_l) \prod_{l \notin c} P_l,$$

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(where S_k^* denotes the power set minus the empty set and singletons) converges in probability to zero, and that $\sqrt{n}(H_n - F_{1n} \cdots F_{kn})$ has the same asymptotic distribution as

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{c \in S_k^*} \prod_{l \in c} (U_{il} - P_l) \prod_{l \notin c} P_l.$$

We can write this as $\sum_{i=1}^n Y_i / \sqrt{(n)}$ where

$$Y_i = \sum_{c \in S_k^*} \prod_{l \in c} (U_{il} - P_l) \prod_{l \notin c} P_l.$$

Under independence, the Y_i 's are i.i.d with mean zero, so that $\sqrt{n}(H_n - F_{1n} \cdots F_{kn})$ is asymptotically normal with zero mean and asymptotic variance

$$\text{Var} \left(\sum_{c \in S_k^*} \prod_{l \in c} (U_{il} - P_l) \prod_{l \notin c} P_l \right).$$

To compute the variance, we note that terms in this sum with different subsets are uncorrelated (which follows from the fact that if random variables X , Y and Z are independent with zero means, then $\text{Cov}(XY, XZ) = 0$). Thus the asymptotic variance is

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{c \in S_k^*} \text{Var} \left(\prod_{l \in c} (U_{il} - P_l) \prod_{l \notin c} P_l \right) &= \sum_{c \in S_k^*} \left(\prod_{l \notin c} P_l \right)^2 \prod_{l \in c} \text{Var}(U_{il} - P_l) \\ &= \sum_{c \in S_k^*} \left(\prod_{l \notin c} P_l \right)^2 \prod_{l \in c} (P_l(1 - P_l)) \\ &= \prod_{l=1}^k P_l \sum_{c \in S_k^*} \left(\prod_{l \notin c} P_l \prod_{l \in c} (1 - P_l) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Note that

$$\sum_{c \in S_k} \prod_{l \notin c} P_l \prod_{l \in c} (1 - P_l) = \prod_{l=1}^k (1 - P_l + P_l) = 1$$

so that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{c \in S_k^*} \prod_{l \notin c} P_l \prod_{l \in c} (1 - P_l) &= 1 - \prod_{l=1}^k P_l - \sum_{j=1}^k \prod_{l \neq j} (1 - P_j) P_l \\ &= 1 - \prod_{l=1}^k P_l - \sum_{j=1}^k \prod_{l=1}^k P_l (1 - P_j) / P_j \\ &= 1 - \prod_{l=1}^k P_l \left(1 + \sum_{j=1}^k (1 - P_j) / P_j \right). \end{aligned}$$

¹⁵ Combining this with equation(1) gives the result.

2. PROOF OF EQUATION(8) OF THE PAPER

We have

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_1(u, H_n) = & n^{-4} \sum_{i_1=1}^n \sum_{i_2=1}^n \sum_{i_3=1}^n \sum_{i_4=1}^n \frac{1}{5} \{ \phi(u, U_{i_1}, U_{i_2}, U_{i_3}, U_{i_4}) + \phi(U_{i_1}, u, U_{i_2}, U_{i_3}, U_{i_4}) \\ & + \cdots + \phi(U_{i_1}, U_{i_2}, U_{i_3}, U_{i_4}, u) - V_n \}. \end{aligned}$$

We evaluate each of these five terms in turn.

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First term:

$$\begin{aligned} n^{-4} \sum_{i_1=1}^n \cdots \sum_{i_4=1}^n \phi(u, U_{i_1}, U_{i_2}, U_{i_3}, U_{i_4}) &= n^{-4} \sum_{i_1=1}^n \cdots \sum_{i_4=1}^n \psi(u, U_{i_1}, U_{i_2}) \psi(u, U_{i_3}, U_{i_4}) \\ &= \left\{ n^{-2} \sum_{i_1=1}^n \sum_{i_2=1}^n \psi(u, U_{i_1}, U_{i_2}) \right\}^2 \\ &= (H_n(x, y) - F_n(x)G_n(y))^2 \\ &= T_1(x, y). \end{aligned}$$

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Second term:

$$\begin{aligned} n^{-4} \sum_{i_1=1}^n \cdots \sum_{i_4=1}^n \phi((U_{i_1}, u, U_{i_2}, U_{i_3}, U_{i_4})) \\ &= n^{-4} \sum_{i_1=1}^n \cdots \sum_{i_4=1}^n \psi(U_{i_1}, u, U_{i_2}) \psi(U_{i_1}, U_{i_3}, U_{i_4}) \\ &= n^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (I(x \odot X_i) I(y \odot Y_i) - (x \odot X_i) G_n(Y_i)) (H_n(X_i, Y_i) - F_n(X_i) G_n(Y_i)) \\ &= T_2(x, y). \end{aligned}$$

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Third term:

$$\begin{aligned} n^{-4} \sum_{i_1=1}^n \cdots \sum_{i_4=1}^n \phi((U_{i_1}, U_{i_2}, u, U_{i_3}, U_{i_4})) \\ &= n^{-4} \sum_{i_1=1}^n \cdots \sum_{i_4=1}^n \psi(U_{i_1}, U_{i_2}, u) \psi(U_{i_1}, U_{i_3}, U_{i_4}) \\ &= n^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (H_n(X_i, Y_i) - F_n(X_i) I(y \odot Y_i)) (H_n(X_i, Y_i) - F_n(X_i) G_n(Y_i)) \\ &= T_3(x, y). \end{aligned}$$

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Fourth term: Same as the second term.

Fifth term: Same as the third term.

3. ASYMPTOTIC DISTRIBUTIONS

In this section we derive the asymptotic distribution of the sum of squared (unnormalized) chi-values in the bivariate and trivariate cases. We first consider the use of regular orthants and then modify the results to cover generalized orthants.

3.1. Bivariate case, regular orthants

The mean of the squared chi-values, denoted by V_n in Section 6.1, is exactly the statistic used in a test of independence introduced in Hoefding (1948), where its asymptotic distribution is discussed. Unfortunately the solution given in Hoefding's paper is incorrect. Below we derive the correct asymptotic distribution using the theory of U-statistics.

As noted in Section 6.1 of the paper,

$$V_n = \frac{1}{n^5} \sum_{i_1=1}^n \cdots \sum_{i_5=1}^n \phi(U_{i_1}, \dots, U_{i_5})$$

where

$$\phi(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_5) = \psi(u_1, u_2, u_3)\psi(u_1, u_4, u_5)$$

and

$$\psi(u_1, u_2, u_3) = I(x_2 \leq x_1)I(y_2 \leq y_1) - I(x_2 \leq x_1)I(y_3 \leq y_1),$$

$u_i = (x_i, y_i)$.

The asymptotic distribution of V_n and the associated U-statistic U_n depends on the quantities $E[U_n]$ and

$$\phi_1(u) = E[\phi_s(u, U_2, \dots, U_5)], \quad (2)$$

$$\phi_2(u_1, u_2) = E[\phi_s(u_1, u_2, \dots, U_5)] \quad (3)$$

where U_2, \dots, U_5 are independently distributed as H , and ϕ_s is the symmetrized version of ϕ . Note that ϕ_s depends only on the ranks of the data, so without loss of generality we can assume that the X 's and Y 's are uniformly distributed.

We first show that under independence, the expected value of U_n is zero. Since all the terms in the expectation of the U-statistic are of the form $E[\psi(U_{i_1}, U_{i_2}, U_{i_3})\psi(U_{i_1}, U_{i_4}, U_{i_5})]$ for i.i.d. U_i , and thus identical, it is enough to show that

$$E[\psi(U_1, U_2, U_3)\psi(U_1, U_4, U_5)] = 0.$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} E[\psi(U_1, U_2, U_3)\psi(U_1, U_4, U_5)] &= \int_0^1 E[\psi(u, U_2, U_3)\psi(u, U_4, U_5)] du \\ &= \int_0^1 E[\psi(u, U_2, U_3)]E[\psi(u, U_4, U_5)] du \\ &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

since $E[\phi(u, U_2, U_3)] = 0$ under independence.

We next compute $\phi_1(u)$ under the assumption of independence of X and Y . We will show that $\phi_1(u) = 0$ for all u . We have

$$\begin{aligned}\phi_1(u) &= E[\phi_s(u, U_2, \dots, U_5)] \\ &= \frac{1}{5!} \{E[(\phi(u, U_2, \dots, U_5))] + \dots + E[\phi(U_5, \dots, U_2, u)]\} \\ &= \frac{1}{5} \{E[\phi(u, U_2, \dots, U_5)] + \dots + E[\phi(U_2, \dots, U_5, u)]\}\end{aligned}$$

since the U 's are i.i.d. The 5 terms in the final sum differ only in the position of u in the argument list. Moreover, since 60

$$E[\psi(u, U_2, U_3)] = E[\psi(U_2, u, U_3)] = E[\psi(U_2, U_3, u)] = 0, \quad (4)$$

it follows that $\phi_1(u) = 0$ for all u , and the U -statistic has first order degeneracy.

Next we compute ϕ_2 . Since the expectations $E[\phi(u_1, u_2, U_3, \dots, U_5)]$, $E[\phi(U_3, u_1, u_2, U_4, U_5)]$ and so on depend only on the positions (i, j) of u_1 and u_2 in the argument list, there are only $5!/3!$ different terms in the sum

$$E[\phi_s(u_1, u_2, \dots, U_5)] = \frac{1}{5!} \{E[(\phi(u_1, u_2, U_3, U_5, U_5))] + \dots + E[\phi(U_5, U_4, U_3, u_2, u_1)]\}.$$

Because of (4), only the terms corresponding to positions (2,4), (2,5), (3,4), (3,5), (4,2), (5,2), (4,3) and (5,3) are non-zero. For these terms, e.g. the (2,4) term, we have

$$\begin{aligned}E[\phi(U_3, u_1, U_4, u_2, U_5)] &= E[\psi(U_3, u_1, U_4)\psi(U_3, u_2, U_5)] \\ &= \int_0^1 E[\psi(u, u_1, U_4)\psi(u, u_2, U_5)] du \\ &= \int_0^1 T_1(u, u_1)T_1(u, u_2) du\end{aligned}$$

say, where $T_1(u, v) = E[\psi(u, v, U_4)]$. Similarly the (2,5) term is $\int_0^1 T_1(u, u_1)T_2(u, u_2) du$, the (3,4) term is $\int_0^1 T_2(u, u_1)T_1(u, u_2) du$, and the (3,5) term is $\int_0^1 T_2(u, u_1)T_2(u, u_2) du$, where $T_2(u, v) = E[\psi(u, U_4, v)]$. The others are computed similarly. Adding these eight terms together gives

$$2 \int_0^1 (T_1(u, u_1) + T_2(u, u_1))(T_1(u, u_2) + T_2(u, u_2)) du$$

so that 65

$$E[(\phi(u_1, u_2, U_3, \dots, U_5))] = \frac{1}{10} \int_0^1 (T_1(u, u_1) + T_2(u, u_1))(T_1(u, u_2) + T_2(u, u_2)) du. \quad (5)$$

If X and Y are independent then, setting $u = (x, y)$, $u_1 = (x_1, y_1)$, and $u_2 = (x_2, y_2)$ we get

$$T_1(u, u_1) + T_2(u, u_1) = (I(x_1 \leq x) - x)(I(y_1 \leq y) - y)$$

and so

$$\phi_2(u_1, u_2) = \frac{1}{10} K(x_1, x_2) K(y_1, y_2)$$

where K is the symmetric kernel

$$\begin{aligned} K(x_1, x_2) &= \int_0^1 (I(x_1 \leq x) - x)(I(x_2 \leq x) - x) dx \\ &= (x_1^2 + x_2^2)/2 - \max(x_1, x_2) + 1/3. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

According to the asymptotic theory of U-statistics with $E[U_n] = 0$, $\phi_1 = 0$ and ϕ_2 non-constant, the asymptotic distribution of nU_n is that of

$$10 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \mu_k (Z_k^2 - 1) \quad (7)$$

where the μ_k 's are the eigenvalues of the integral operator with kernel

$$\frac{1}{10} K(x_1, x_2) K(y_1, y_2)$$

70 and the Z_k 's are iid $N(0, 1)$ random variables. (Note that the factor $1/10$ and 10 cancel out so we can ignore them in what follows.) We can use the representation (7) to approximate the characteristic function of the limit distribution, and hence the distribution function via numerical inversion of the cf. Since the kernel is a product, its eigenvalues are of the form $\lambda_i \lambda_j$ where the λ_i 's are the eigenvalues of K . Thus we can write the asymptotic distribution of nU_n as

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_m \lambda_n (Z_{m,n}^2 - 1) \quad (8)$$

75 where the $Z_{m,n}$ are i.i.d $N(0, 1)$.

Eigenvalues of K

To find the eigenvalues, we first expand the function

$$A(t, s) = I(s \leq t) - t$$

in a (complex) Fourier series as a function of t . We get

$$A(t, s) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} c_n(s) e^{2\pi n t}.$$

Since the complex exponentials are orthonormal on $[0, 1]$,

$$\begin{aligned} c_0(s) &= \int_0^1 A(t, s) dt = 1/2 - s, \text{ and} \\ c_n(s) &= \int_0^1 A(t, s) e^{-2\pi n t} dt = e^{-2\pi n s} / (2\pi i n), n = \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots \end{aligned}$$

and so

$$A(t, s) = 1/2 - s + \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-2\pi i n (t-s)}}{2\pi i n}.$$

Using this, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
K(s_1, s_2) &= \int_0^1 A(t, s_1) \overline{A(t, s_2)} dt \\
&= \int_0^1 \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} c_m(s_1) \overline{c_n(s_2)} e^{-2\pi i(m-n)t} dt \\
&= \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} c_n(s_1) \overline{c_n(s_2)}. \tag{9}
\end{aligned}$$

From this equation, again using the orthogonality, we get

$$\int_0^1 K(s_1, s_2) \cos(2\pi n s_2) ds_2 = \frac{1}{4\pi^2 n^2} \cos(2\pi n s_1)$$

so that $\cos(2\pi n s_1)$ is an eigenfunction with eigenvalue $\frac{1}{4\pi^2 n^2}$.

We note that K is symmetric and positive definite so all the eigenvalues are real and positive. The sum of the eigenvalues is given by

$$\int_0^1 K(s, s) ds = \int_0^1 \int_0^1 (I(s \leq t) - t)^2 dt ds = 1/6.$$

On the other hand,

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{4\pi^2 n^2} = \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \frac{\pi^2}{6} = \frac{1}{24} < \frac{1}{6},$$

so there must be some more eigenvalues. To find these, we once again use (9). The kernel K is approximated by the kernel K_N given by

$$K(s_1, s_2)_N = \sum_{n=-N}^N c_n(s_1) \overline{c_n(s_2)}$$

By the the theory of Freedholm integral equations, the eigenvalues of the kernel K_N are just the eigenvalues of the matrix with m, n entries

$$\int_0^1 c_m(s) \overline{c_n(s)} ds. \tag{10}$$

The functions $c_n(s)$ are orthogonal except for $c_0(s)$ for which

$$\int_0^1 c_0(s) \overline{c_n(s)} ds = 1/(4\pi^2 n^2)$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_0^1 c_0(s) \overline{c_0(s)} ds &= 1/12, \\
\int_0^1 c_n(s) \overline{c_n(s)} ds &= 1/(4\pi^2 n^2), n \neq 0.
\end{aligned}$$

It follows that the matrix with elements (10) in our case takes the form

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B' & D \end{bmatrix}$$

where

$$A = \text{diag} \left(1/(4\pi^2 N^2), 1/(4\pi^2 (N-1)^2), \dots, 1/(4\pi^2 N^2) \right),$$

D is of the form

$$D = \begin{bmatrix} 1/12 & d' \\ d & E \end{bmatrix}$$

where $d' = (1/(4\pi^2), 1/(4\pi^2 2^2), \dots, 1/(4\pi^2 N^2))$, $E = \text{diag}(d)$, and B has all entries zero except for the first column which has entries those of the vector b where

$$b' = \left(1/(4\pi^2 N^2), 1/(4\pi^2 (N-1)^2), \dots, 1/4\pi^2 \right).$$

We can exchange the “ $-N$ ” and “zero” rows and columns of M without changing the eigenvalues, so we now need to solve the equation

$$\det \begin{bmatrix} 1/12 - \lambda & v' \\ v & \text{diag}(v) - \lambda I \end{bmatrix} = 0,$$

where $v' = (b', d')$. Using the formula

$$\det \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B' & D \end{bmatrix} = \det(D) \det(A - BD^{-1}B')$$

we get

$$\det(M - \lambda I) = \prod_{n=1}^N (1/(4\pi^2 n^2) \lambda)^2 (1/12 - \lambda - 2 \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{1}{4\pi^2 n^2} \left(1 - \frac{\lambda}{4\pi^2 n^2} \right)^{-1})$$

Now suppose λ is an eigenvalue not equal to $\frac{1}{4\pi n^2}$ for some n between 1 and N . Then λ satisfies the equation $\det(M - \lambda I) = 0$. Since the product above cannot be zero (λ is not equal to $\frac{1}{4\pi n^2}$, $n = 1, \dots, N$), λ must be a solution of

$$d(\lambda) = 1/12 - \lambda - 2 \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{1}{4\pi^2 n^2} \left(1 - \frac{\lambda}{4\pi^2 n^2} \right)^{-1} = 0.$$

Furthermore, we see that the function $d(\lambda)$ has vertical asymptotes at the points $\lambda = 1/(4\pi^2 n^2)$, $n = 1, \dots, N$, and that between successive asymptotes, the derivative of d is negative, since

$$d'(\lambda) = -1 - 2 \sum_{n=1}^N \left(1 - \frac{\lambda}{4\pi^2 n^2} \right)^{-2} < 0$$

⁸⁵ Thus, we can find the other eigenvalues numerically by repeatedly using a simple root-finding scheme with endpoints $1/(4\pi^2 (n+1)^2)$ and $1/(\pi^2 n^2)$. Alternatively, we may simply use a standard numerical method to find the eigenvalues of M .

Relationship between $E[nV_n]$ and $E[nU_n]$

From U -statistic theory (see e.g Lee (1990) p. 183) we can write

$$n^5 V_n = 5! S_5^{(5)} \binom{n}{5} U_n + 4! S_5^{(4)} \binom{n}{5} W_n + o_p(1) \quad (11)$$

where $\mathcal{S}_k^{(j)}$ is the Stirling number of the second kind, and W_n is a U -statistic with kernel

$$\phi_W(u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4) = \frac{1}{4! \mathcal{S}_5^{(4)}} \sum^* \phi(u_{i_1}, u_{i_2}, u_{i_3}, u_{i_4}, u_{i_5})$$

and the sum \sum^* is taken over all $4! \mathcal{S}_5^{(4)}$ 5-tuples of 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 with exactly four indices distinct. Since $\mathcal{S}_5^{(4)} = 10$ there are 240 elements in the sum defining the kernel of W_n . Thus, using the fact that $\mathcal{S}_5^{(5)} = 1$, and the weak law of large numbers for U -statistics, equation(11) becomes 90

$$nV_n = nU_n + 10E[W_n] + o_p(1) \quad (12)$$

so that, up to a constant, the asymptotic distributions of nV_n and nU_n are the same.

To compute this constant, note that $E(W_n)$ is the average of 240 terms of the form $E[\phi(U_{i_1}, U_{i_2}, U_{i_3}, U_{i_4}, U_{i_5})]$. Since the U 's are i.i.d., the value of these terms depends only on the position of the repeated index. Thus there are only $\binom{5}{2} = 10$ separate values, corresponding to the number of ways we can choose the positions of the repeated index. Each value is repeated 24 times. 95

To evaluate these, consider $E[\phi(U_1, U_2, U_3, U_4, U_5)]$. Direct calculation using the definition of ϕ shows that this can be written as 100

$$A(1, 2, 4)A(1, 2, 4) - A(1, 2, 4)A(1, 2, 5) - A(1, 2, 4)A(1, 3, 4) + A(1, 2, 4)A(1, 3, 5) \quad (13)$$

where

$$A(j, k, l) = E[I(X_{i_k} \leq X_{i_j})I(X_{i_l} \leq X_{i_j})] = E[I(Y_{i_k} \leq Y_{i_j})I(Y_{i_l} \leq Y_{i_j})] = E[I(Z_{i_k} \leq Z_{i_j})I(Z_{i_l} \leq Z_{i_j})].$$

A simple calculation shows that

$$A(i, j, k) = \begin{cases} 1/2, & \text{if exactly 2 of } i, j, k \text{ are equal,} \\ 1/3, & \text{if all of } i, j, k \text{ are distinct,} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

(Which, incidentally, shows that $E[\phi(U_1, U_2, U_3, U_4, U_5)] = 0$.) Now consider what happens when one index is repeated, say $E[\phi(U_1, U_2, U_2, U_4, U_5)]$. We can calculate this expectation by replacing 3 with 2 in (13) and using (14): the expectation is zero. Evaluating the other nine cases and adding the results gives a total of 1/36 so that the expectation of W_n is $(1/36 \times 24/240 = 1/360$ and so 105

$$nV_n = nU_n + 1/36 + o_p(1)$$

Finally, note that the sum of the eigenvalues of K is

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \lambda_i = \int_0^1 \int_0^1 K(s, s) ds = 1/6$$

so that the sum of the eigenvalues $\lambda_i \lambda_j$ is 1/36. This shows that the asymptotic distribution of nV_n is

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_m \lambda_n Z_{m,n}^2.$$

3.2. Trivariate case, regular orthants

We first derive the asymptotic distribution when the chi-values are computed using regular orthants. We then show how this must be modified when generalized orthants are used. Now let

X, Y, Z be a trivariate random vector with joint df $H(x, y, z)$ and marginal df's $H_1(x), H_2(y), H_3(z)$. The mean of the unnormalized squared chi-values is

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (H_n(X_i, Y_i, Z_i) - H_{1n}(X_i)H_{2n}(Y_i)H_{3n}(Z_i))^2$$

where $H_{1,n}, H_{2,n}, H_{3,n}$, are the empirical df's. Once again we can express this as a V -statistic in the trivariate r.vs $U_i = (X_i, Y_i, Z_i)$:

$$V_n = \frac{1}{n^7} \sum_{i_1=1}^n \sum_{i_2=1}^n \sum_{i_3=1}^n \sum_{i_4=1}^n \sum_{i_5=1}^n \sum_{i_6=1}^n \sum_{i_7=1}^n \phi(U_{i_1}, U_{i_2}, U_{i_3}, U_{i_4}, U_{i_5}, U_{i_6}, U_{i_7})$$

where the kernel ϕ is

$$\phi(u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4, u_5, u_6, u_7) = \psi(u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4)\psi(u_1, u_5, u_6, u_7)$$

and

$$\psi(u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4) = I(x_2 \leq x_1)I(y_2 \leq y_1)I(z_2 \leq z_1) - I(x_2 \leq x_1)I(y_3 \leq y_1)I(z_4 \leq z_1).$$

110 As in Section 3.1, the statistic nV_n is exactly the sum of the squared unnormalized chi-values. To find its asymptotic distribution, we follow the same strategy as before: we relate it to a U -statistic U_n and then find the asymptotic distribution of U_n .

Relationship with U_n

115 Let ϕ_s be the symmetrized version of ϕ and U_n the U -statistic based on ϕ_s . Then, as in Section 3.1, we have

$$n^7 V_n = 7! \mathcal{S}_7^{(7)} \binom{n}{7} U_n + 7! \mathcal{S}_7^{(6)} \binom{n}{6} W_n + o_p(n^6) \quad (15)$$

where W_n is the U -statistic based on the kernel

$$\phi_W(u_1, \dots, u_6) = \frac{1}{6! \mathcal{S}_7^{(6)}} \sum \phi(u_{i_1}, u_{i_2}, u_{i_3}, u_{i_4}, u_{i_5}, u_{i_6}, u_{i_7})$$

and the sum is taken over all $6! \mathcal{S}_7^{(6)}$ 7-tuples $(i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5, i_6, i_7)$ chosen from $1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6$ with exactly two repeats. Since $\mathcal{S}_7^{(6)} = 21$, (15) implies

$$nV_n = nU_n + 21E(W_n) + o_p(1). \quad (16)$$

120 Thus, to establish the asymptotic distribution of nV_n , we need to compute $\phi_1(u) = E[\phi_s(u, U_2, U_3, U_4, U_5, U_6, U_7)]$, $\phi_2(u_1, u_2) = E[\phi_s(u_1, u_2, U_3, U_4, U_5, U_6, U_7)]$ and $E[W_n]$.

Calculation of $E[W_n]$ under independence

Arguing as in Section 3.1, we see that

$$\begin{aligned} E[\phi(S)(U_1, U_2, U_3, U_4, U_5, U_6, U_7)] &= A[1, 2, 5]A[1, 2, 5]A[1, 2, 5] \\ &\quad - A[1, 2, 5]A[1, 2, 6]A[1, 2, 7] - A[1, 2, 5]A[1, 3, 5]A[1, 4, 5] \\ &\quad + A[1, 2, 5]A[1, 3, 6]A[1, 4, 7] \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Again, the value of the expectation when there are two repeated indices depends only in the positions of the repeats, so there are only $\binom{7}{2} = 21$ possible values for the expectation. There are $6!S_7^{(6)} = 720 \times 21 = 15120$ terms in the sum defining ϕ_{S_2} so each value is repeated 720 times. To evaluate the expectation when the repeats are in positions i and j , any such arrangement will suffice. We pick a standard set of indices created from 1,2,3,4,5,6,7 by replacing the digit in position j using the digit in position i . Thus e.g. if $i = 2$ and $j = 4$ we use 1,2,3,2,5,6,7. 130

Thus we need to compute (17), replacing i with j , for each of the 21 unordered pairs (i, j) , $i, j = 1, \dots, 7, i \neq j$. This gives a total of 7/216 so that $E[W_n] = (720 \times 7 / (216)) / (720 \times 21) = 7 / (216 \times 21)$, hence by (16),

$$nV_n = nU_n + 7/216 + o_p(1).$$

Asymptotic distribution

We now assume that X, Y and Z are independent and note that since the kernel ψ depends only on the order of the observations and not on their actual values, we may assume that X, Y , and Z are uniformly distributed on $[0,1]$. Also, since 135

$$E[\psi(u, U_2, U_3, U_4)] = E[\psi(U_1, u, U_3, U_4)] = E[\psi(U_2, U_2, u, U_4)] = E[\psi(U_2, U_2, U_3, u)] = 0 \quad (18)$$

which, by the arguments of Section 3.1, shows that $\phi_1(u) = 0$.

We use the same arguments as before for ϕ_2 . We have

$$\phi_2(u, v) = \frac{1}{7!} \{E[\phi(u, v, U_{i_1}, \dots, U_{i_5})] + \dots + E[\phi(U_{i_1}, \dots, U_{i_5}, v, u)]\}$$

There are $7! = 5040$ terms in this sum corresponding to all $5!$ possible permutations (i_1, \dots, i_5) of $(1, \dots, 5)$ and all 42 possible positions of u and v . However, the U 's are i.i.d so there are only 42 possible values of these terms, corresponding to the positions (i, j) of u and v . For example, by (18) and the arguments of Section 3.1, the terms $(1, j)$ and $(j, 1)$ are zero for $j = 2, \dots, 7$. Also, if i and j are both between 2 and 4, or both between 5 and 7, the term is zero. This leaves 18 terms nine of which are shown in Table 1. The function $\phi_2(u, v)$ can be expressed in terms of the quantities 140
 $T_1(u, v) = E[\psi(u, v, U_3, U_4)]$, $T_2(u, v) = E[\psi(u, U_3, v, U_4)]$ and $T_3(u, v) = E[\psi(u, U_3, U_4, v)]$ 145
as indicated in Table 1.

Positions	Value of term
$i = 2, j = 5$	$\int_0^1 T_1(t, u)T_1(t, v), dt$
$i = 2, j = 6$	$\int_0^1 T_1(t, u)T_2(t, v), dt$
$i = 2, j = 7$	$\int_0^1 T_1(t, u)T_3(t, v), dt$
$i = 3, j = 5$	$\int_0^1 T_2(t, u)T_1(t, v), dt$
$i = 3, j = 6$	$\int_0^1 T_2(t, u)T_2(t, v), dt$
$i = 3, j = 7$	$\int_0^1 T_2(t, u)T_3(t, v), dt$
$i = 4, j = 5$	$\int_0^1 T_3(t, u)T_1(t, v), dt$
$i = 4, j = 6$	$\int_0^1 T_3(t, u)T_2(t, v), dt$
$i = 4, j = 7$	$\int_0^1 T_3(t, u)T_3(t, v), dt$

Table 1. Values of the nine terms.

Summing these nine terms, we get

$$\int_0^1 T(t, u)T(t, v), dt$$

150 where $T = T_1 + T_2 + T_3$. This is symmetric in (u, v) so the other nine terms corresponding to $i = 5, j = 2, i = 6, j = 2$ and so on sum to the same value. Thus, finally

$$\phi_2(u, v) = \binom{7}{2}^{-1} \int_0^1 T(t, u)T(t, v), dt. \quad (19)$$

Direct calculation gives, writing $u = (x, y, z)$ and $u_1 = (x_1, y_1, z_1)$,

$$\begin{aligned} T_1(u, u_1) &= (I(x_1) \leq x)(I(y_1) \leq y)(I(z_1) \leq z) + x(I(y_1) \leq y)(I(z_1) \leq z) \\ &\quad + z(I(x_1) \leq x)(I(y_1) \leq y) + y(I(x_1) \leq x)(I(z_1) \leq z) \\ &\quad + xI(y_1) \leq y)z + xyI(z_1) \leq z), \end{aligned}$$

$$T_2(u, u_1) = -xzI(y_1) \leq y), \text{ and}$$

$$T_3(u, u_1) = -xyI(z_1) \leq z).$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} T(u, u_1) &= A(x, x_1)A(y, y_1)A(z, z_1) + xA(y, y_1)A(z, z_1) \\ &\quad + A(x, x_1)yA(z, z_1) + A(x, x_1)A(y, y_1)z. \end{aligned}$$

where $A(t, s) = I(s \leq t) - t$. Substituting these values into (19) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_2(u_1, u_2) &= \binom{7}{2}^{-1} \{K(x_1, x_2)K(y_1, y_2)K(z_1, z_2) + [L(x_1) + L(x_2)]K(y_1, y_2)K(z_1, z_2) \\ &\quad + [L(y_1) + L(y_2)]K(x_1, x_2)K(z_1, z_2) + (L(z_1) + L(z_2))K(x_1, x_2)K(y_1, y_2) \\ &\quad + [L(x_1)L(y_2) + L(x_2)L(y_1)]K(z_1, z_2) + (L(y_1)L(z_2) + L(y_2)L(z_1))K(x_1, x_2) \\ &\quad + [L(y_1)L(z_2) + L(y_2)L(z_1)]K(x_1, x_2) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{3} [K(x_1, x_2)K(y_1, y_2) + K(x_1, x_2)K(z_1, z_2) + K(y_1, y_2)K(z_1, z_2)]\} \quad (20) \end{aligned}$$

where K is the kernel (6) considered in Section 3.1 and

$$L(s) = \int_0^1 t(I(S \leq t) - t) dt = (1 - s^2)/2 - 1/3.$$

155 To find the eigenvalues of $\phi_{S^2}(u_1, u_2)$, we can use two methods. The first approximates the integral equation using a quadrature formula. If we use a simple mid-point rule this amounts to approximating the integral equation with a matrix eigenvalue problem, where the eigenvalues are approximated by the eigenvalues of the matrix with entries $\phi_{S^2}(u_1, u_2)/N^3$, with $u_1 = (s_j, s_k, s_l)$, $u_2 = (s_{j'}, s_{k'}, s_{l'})$, and s_1, s_2, \dots are N equally spaced values between 0 and 1.

In a second approach, we expand the function t as a Fourier series:

$$t = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} d_n e^{2\pi n t}$$

where

$$d_n = \int_0^1 t e^{-2\pi n t} dt = -1/(2\pi i n).$$

This gives, along with the Fourier series for $(I(s \leq t) - t)$ already considered,

$$T(u, u_1) = \sum_{j=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{l=-\infty}^{\infty} C_{jkl}(x_1, y_1, z_1) e^{2\pi i(jx+ky+lz)}$$

where

$$C_{jkl}(x, y, z) = c_j(x)c_k(y)c_l(z) + c_j(x)c_k(y)d_l + c_j(x)d_k c_l(z)d + d_j c_k(y)c_l(z).$$

Substituting this into (19) and using the orthogonality of the complex exponentials gives

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$$\phi_2(u_1, u_2) = \sum_{j=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{l=-\infty}^{\infty} C_{jkl}(x_1, y_1, z_1) \overline{C_{jkl}(x_2, y_2, z_2)}$$

As in Section 3.1, we approximate this kernel by

$$\phi_{2,N}(u_1, u_2) = \sum_{j=-N}^N \sum_{k=-N}^N \sum_{l=-N}^N C_{jkl}(x_1, y_1, z_1) \overline{C_{jkl}(x_2, y_2, z_2)}$$

The eigenvalues of $\phi_{2,N}$ are those of the matrix M say with $(j, k, l; j', k', l')$ element

$$\int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 C_{jkl}(x, y, z) \overline{C_{j'k'l'}(x, y, z)} dx dy dz.$$

Note that the order of the triple indices in the sum (and in the rows and columns of M is immaterial, as the eigenvalues of a matrix are invariant under (identical) permutations of the rows and columns.

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To evaluate the elements of M , we note that

$$\int_0^1 c_j(s) \overline{c_k(s)} ds = \begin{cases} 0, & j \neq k, j \neq 0, k \neq 0 \\ 1/(4\pi^2 j^2), & j = k, j \neq 0, k \neq 0; \\ 1/(4\pi^2 j^2), & j \neq 0, k = 0; \\ 1/(4\pi^2 k^2), & j = 0, k \neq 0; \\ 1/12, & j = 0, k = 0. \end{cases}$$

and

$$\int_0^1 c_0(s) ds = 0.$$

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Now let C and D be the matrices with (j, k) element $\int_0^1 c_j(s) \overline{c_k(s)} ds$ and $d_j \overline{d_k}$ respectively. Then the $(j, k, l; j', k', l')$ element of M is

$$C_{jj'} C_{kk'} C_{ll'} + C_{jj'} C_{kk'} D_{ll'} + C_{jj'} D_{kk'} C_{ll'} + D_{jj'} C_{kk'} C_{ll'}$$

Since the ordering of the triples is arbitrary, we can express a (possibly reordered) version of M in terms of Kronecker products as

$$M = C \otimes C \otimes C + C \otimes C \otimes D + C \otimes D \otimes C + D \otimes C \otimes C.$$

To compute the eigenvalues of M , note that the matrix M is quite sparse, although of high dimension, for example, with $N = 10$, the matrix is of dimension $(2N + 1)^3 \times (2N + 1)^3$ or 9261×9261 . This suggests we might use a sparse matrix package to compute the eigenvalues.

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3.3. Bivariate case, generalized orthants

In this case the chi-value does not depend on which of the four possible orthants are used in its calculation, so the asymptotic distribution is the same, irrespective of whether regular or generalized orthants are used.

3.4. Trivariate case, generalized orthants

In this case we have eight orthants corresponding to the eight choices of \leq or $>$ in the sets $(x \odot \frac{1}{2}, y \odot \frac{1}{2}, z \odot \frac{1}{2})$ where \odot can be either \leq or $>$. The V -statistic based on these generalized orthants has kernel

$$\phi^*(u, u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4, u_5, u_6) = \psi^*(u, u_1, u_2, u_3)\psi^*(u, u_4, u_5, u_6)$$

where ψ^* is defined in the eight regions analogously to the last section:

Region	$\psi^*(u, u_1, u_2, u_3)$
$R_1 : x \geq 0.5, y \geq 0.5, z \geq 0.5$	$I(x_1 \leq x)I(y_1 \leq y)I(z_1 \leq z) - I(x_1 \leq x)I(y_2 \leq y)I(z_3 \leq z)$
$R_2 : x \geq 0.5, y \geq 0.5, z < 0.5$	$I(x_1 \leq x)I(y_1 \leq y)I(z_1 > z) - I(x_1 \leq x)I(y_2 \leq y)I(z_3 > z)$
$R_3 : x \geq 0.5, y < 0.5, z \geq 0.5$	$I(x_1 \leq x)I(y_1 > y)I(z_1 \leq z) - I(x_1 \leq x)I(y_2 > y)I(z_3 \leq z)$
$R_4 : x \geq 0.5, y < 0.5, z < 0.5$	$I(x_1 \leq x)I(y_1 > y)I(z_1 > z) - I(x_1 \leq x)I(y_2 > y)I(z_3 > z)$
$R_5 : x < 0.5, y \geq 0.5, z \geq 0.5$	$I(x_1 > x)I(y_1 \leq y)I(z_1 \leq z) - I(x_1 > x)I(y_2 \leq y)I(z_3 \leq z)$
$R_6 : x < 0.5, y \geq 0.5, z < 0.5$	$I(x_1 > x)I(y_1 \leq y)I(z_1 > z) - I(x_1 > x)I(y_2 \leq y)I(z_3 > z)$
$R_7 : x < 0.5, y < 0.5, z \geq 0.5$	$I(x_1 > x)I(y_1 \leq y)I(z_1 \leq z) - I(x_1 > x)I(y_2 \leq y)I(z_3 \leq z)$
$R_8 : x < 0.5, y < 0.5, z < 0.5$	$I(x_1 > x)I(y_1 > y)I(z_1 > z) - I(x_1 > x)I(y_2 > y)I(z_3 > z)$

Now define $T_1^*(u, u_1) = E[\psi^*(u, u_1, U_1, U_2)]$, $T_2^*(u, u_1) = E[\psi^*(u, U_1, u_1, U_2)]$, $T_3^*(u, u_1) = E[\psi^*(u, U_1, U_2, u_1)]$ and $T^* = T_1^* + T_2^* + T_3^*$. Then as in Section 3.2, the kernel of the U -statistic corresponding to V_n is

$$\phi_2^*(u_1, u_2) = \binom{7}{2}^{-1} \int_0^1 T^*(u, u_1)T^*(u, u_2) du. \quad (21)$$

Arguing as in Section 3.2, we get

$$T^*(u, u_1) = A^*(x, x_1)A^*(y, y_1)A^*(z, z_1) + b(x)A^*(y, y_1)A^*(z, z_1) + A^*(x, x_1)b(y)A^*(z, z_1) + A^*(x, x_1)A^*(y, y_1)b(z)$$

where

$$A^*(t, s) = \begin{cases} A(t, s), & s \geq \frac{1}{2} \\ -A(t, s), & s < \frac{1}{2} \end{cases},$$

$$b(t) = \begin{cases} t, & s \geq \frac{1}{2} \\ (1-t), & s < \frac{1}{2} \end{cases}$$

and $\phi_2^*(u_1, u)$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_2^*(u_1, u_2) = & \binom{7}{2}^{-1} \{K^*(x_1, x_2)K^*(y_1, y_2)K^*(z_1, z_2) + [L^*(x_1) + L^*(x_2)]K^*(y_1, y_2)K^*(z_1, z_2) \\ & + [L^*(y_1) + L^*(y_2)]K^*(x_1, x_2)K^*(z_1, z_2) + (L^*(z_1) + L^*(z_2))K^*(x_1, x_2)K^*(y_1, y_2) \\ & + [L^*(x_1)L^*(y_2) + L^*(x_2)L^*(y_1)]K^*(z_1, z_2) + (L^*(y_1)L^*(z_2) + L^*(y_2)L^*(z_1))K^*(x_1, x_2) \\ & + [L^*(y_1)L^*(z_2) + L^*(y_2)L^*(z_1)]K^*(x_1, x_2) \\ & + \frac{7}{12} [K^*(x_1, x_2)K^*(y_1, y_2) + K^*(x_1, x_2)K^*(z_1, z_2) + K^*(y_1, y_2)K^*(z_1, z_2)]\} \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where

$$K^*(s_1, s_2) = \int_0^1 A^*(t, s_1)A^*(t, s_2) ds = \int_0^1 A(t, s_1)A(t, s_2) ds$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} L^*(s) &= \int_0^1 b(t)A^*(t, s) dt \\ &= \begin{cases} 7/24 - s^2/2, & s > 1/2, \\ s - s^2/2 - 5/24, & s < 1/2. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

To calculate the eigenvalues of ϕ_2^* , we can use either of the methods described in Section 3.2. First, we can evaluate the kernel and approximate its eigenvalues by those of the matrix N with entries $\phi_2^*(u_1, u_2)/N$, with $u_1 = (s_j, s_k, s_l)$, $u_2 = (s_{j'}, s_{k'}, s_{l'})$, and s_1, s_2, \dots are N equally spaced values between 0 and 1. 200

Second, we can expand T^* in a Fourier series. We get (writing $u = (x, y, z)$, $u_1 = (x_1, y_1, z_1)$, $u_2 = (x_2, y_2, z_2)$) 205

$$T^*(u, u_1) = \sum_{j=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{l=-\infty}^{\infty} C_{ijk}^*(u_1) \exp(2\pi i(jx + ky + lz))$$

where

$$C_{ijk}^*(u_1) = \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 T^*(u, u_1) \exp(-2\pi i(jx + ky + lz)) dx dy dz.$$

Evaluating the integral, we get

$$C_{ijk}^*(u) = c_j^*(x)c_k^*(y)c_l^*(z) + d_j^*c_k^*(y)c_l^*(z) + c_j^*(x)d_k^*c_l^*(z) + c_j^*(x)c_k^*(y)d_l^*$$

where now

$$\begin{aligned} d_n^* &= \int_0^1 b(t)t \exp(-2\pi int) dt \\ &= \begin{cases} \frac{1-(-1)^n}{2\pi^2 n^2}, & n \neq 0, \\ \frac{3}{4}, & n = 0. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

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and

$$\begin{aligned} c_n^*(s) &= \int_0^1 A^*(t, s) \exp(-2\pi int) dt \\ &= \begin{cases} \frac{i((-1)^n - e^{2\pi ins})}{2\pi n} - \frac{1-(-1)^n}{2\pi^2 n^2}, & n \neq 0, s \geq 0.5, \\ \frac{-i((-1)^n - e^{2\pi ins})}{2\pi n} - \frac{(1-(-1)^n)}{2\pi^2 n^2}, & n \neq 0, s < 0.5, \\ 3/4 - s, & n = 0, s \geq 0.5, \\ s - 1/4, & n = 0, s < 0.5. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the form of the Fourier coefficients is the same as in the case of regular orthants. We get

$$\phi_2^*(u_1, u_2) = \sum_{j=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{l=-\infty}^{\infty} C_{jkl}^*(u_1) \overline{C_{jkl}^*(u_2)} \quad (23)$$

215 If we approximate the kernel ϕ_2^* by taking finite sums in (23), the eigenvalues of the approximating kernel are those of the matrix M with elements

$$M_{jkl,j'k'l'} = \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 C_{jkl}^*(u) \overline{C_{j'k'l'}^*(u)} dx dy dz$$

As in Section 3.2, we can express M as

$$M = C^* \otimes C^* \otimes C^* + D^* \otimes C^* \otimes C^* + C^* \otimes D^* \otimes C^* + C^* \otimes C^* \otimes D^*$$

where C^* is the matrix with elements $\int_0^1 c_m^*(s) \overline{c_n^*(s)} ds$ and D^* has elements $d_m^* \overline{d_n^*}$.

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